

A Laboratory-Based Assessment of Pervious Bituminous Pavement for Urban Drainage

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ABSTRACT—Urban flooding in under-bridge areas poses significant challenges, leading to traffic congestion, road deterioration, and increased maintenance costs. Traditional drainage systems often fail to efficiently manage excess storm water, exacerbating these issues. This study investigates the use of pervious bituminous pavement as an innovative and sustainable drainage solution. By integrating engineered void structures, this pavement allows water infiltration, reducing surface runoff and enhancing groundwater recharge. The research focuses on evaluating its permeability, durability, and overall performance under varying environmental and traffic conditions. Laboratory tests, including softening point, penetration, ductility, soil compaction, and California Bearing Ratio (CBR), were conducted to determine the suitability of the materials. The results demonstrate that pervious bituminous pavement improves drainage efficiency, minimizes hydroplaning risks, and enhances road resilience, making it a viable alternative for under-bridge storm-water management.

Keywords—Pervious bituminous pavement, stormwater management, laboratory test, permeability.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid urbanisation, high rainfall, and poor drainage are all contributing factors to frequent waterlogging, especially in low-lying regions like underpasses, and they are posing an increasing challenge to urban infrastructure. In addition to interfering with transit, these occurrences hasten pavement degradation and raise maintenance expenses. Conventional impermeable pavements make this problem worse by blocking stormwater's natural infiltration, which increases surface runoff and puts strain on the drainage systems that are already in place.

Pervious bituminous pavements have become an inventive and sustainable solution to these problems. By allowing rainfall to percolate through the pavement surface and into the earth, their porous design lowers runoff, encourages groundwater recharge, and lessens the chance of urban flooding. However, a thorough evaluation of these materials' performance in controlled settings is necessary before they can be extensively used. This study focuses on the laboratory assessment of pervious bituminous pavement to determine its suitability for use in stormwater-sensitive zones such as underpasses. A series of tests were conducted on both the bitumen and the supporting

soil to examine key physical and mechanical properties. These include the softening point, ductility, and penetration tests for bitumen, as well as soil compaction, water content determination, and the California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test.

By analyzing the behavior of materials under simulated conditions, this part of the research aims to provide a solid foundation for evaluating how pervious bituminous pavement will perform in real-world applications. The findings from these tests will guide further design, material selection, and future implementation strategies, ultimately supporting the development of more resilient and sustainable urban infrastructure.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, **pervious bituminous pavements** have gained a lot of attention because of their ability to manage stormwater and reduce the risk of flooding in urban areas. These pavements are designed to allow water to pass through them instead of collecting on the surface. This makes them especially useful in **flood-prone areas**, such as **underpasses**, where water often gets trapped during heavy rains. One important thing that researchers agree on is that **laboratory testing** plays a major role in making sure these pavements will actually work as expected. Lab tests help us understand how strong the materials are and how well they can drain water. This is important not only for choosing the right materials but also for making sure the pavement will last long and perform well under different weather and traffic conditions.

Case study 1: Bagade et al. (2019) carried out a detailed study in **Karanjade, Panvel**, where flooding was a major issue. They explored whether pervious bituminous pavement could be a good solution. In their study, they used lab tests like the **California Bearing Ratio (CBR)** test to check the strength of the soil underneath the pavement, which is important for

supporting the load of vehicles. They followed national guidelines from **IRC SP:62 (2014)** for designing the pavement. The results showed that their design could handle **light traffic** and still allow enough water to pass through the surface, which would help prevent flooding. This makes it a smart choice for areas like **underpasses**, which often get flooded during monsoon seasons.

Case study 2: Tang and Jiang (2003), who sssare similar in purpose to bituminous ones. They tested different mix designs in the lab to measure their **permeability** (how easily water can pass through), **compressive strength** (how much weight they can handle), and **durability** (how long they last without breaking down). Their study showed that choosing the right combination of materials is crucial to making a pavement that works well. They concluded that **proper lab testing is essential** to predict how the pavement will perform in real-life conditions and ensure it lasts for a long time.

Case study 3: Wang et al. (2018) suggested a **performance-based evaluation system**, which means they used lab test data to predict how pavements would behave over time. They focused on key bitumen properties like the **softening point** (how heat affects it), **ductility** (how much it can stretch before breaking), and **penetration** (how hard or soft it is). These properties were used to create models that help engineers understand how the pavement will handle **traffic, climate, and aging** over the years. This approach helps in choosing the best materials for a specific location, depending on local weather and how much traffic the road will get.

Together, these studies demonstrate how important laboratory tests are for confirming the structural soundness and environmental compatibility of pervious bituminous pavement. These tests include softening point, standard penetration, ductility, soil compaction, and CBR. The current study's results are consistent with previous research, confirming the necessity of conducting these testing prior to the on-site installation of permeable pavement systems in urban drainage projects.

MATERIAL USED

1. **Porous asphalt** -it is a mixture of fine and coarse aggregate bounded by a bituminous binder. The void space in porous asphalt is 15% to 22%. Grade 25 or grade 35 bitumen used in the design mix.
2. **Choker coarse aggregate** –smaller aggregate passing through 12.5mm and retained on 10mm sieve. This layer is placed on the gravel bed so as used to fill the voids and provide a stable surface for pavement.

3. **Gravel** – consists of clean crushed stone passing through 25mm and retained on 20mm sieve that serves as a structural layer and temporary water storage.
4. **Cock net** – cock net is used to separate the layers and to prevent the migration of fines into the stone bed while allowing water to pass through.
5. **Soil**- The natural ground or prepared subgrade that supports all the pavement layers.
6. **Side Drainage**- Installed with pipes and cock netting to guide and manage water flow.

LABORATORY TEST ON BITUMEN AND SOIL

Mould	1	2
Initial reading	0	0
final reading	78	66.5
	78	66.5

Test on bitumen

Softening Point: The temperature at which bitumen softens and becomes more fluid. It helps assess its performance in hot conditions. A higher softening point means better heat resistance. It is the temperature at which a steel ball, placed on a sample of bitumen inside a ring, begins to sink a specified distance under the influence of gravity.

Standard Penetration Test: Measures bitumen's hardness. A higher value indicates softer bitumen, and a lower value indicates harder bitumen, affecting its suitability for different climates and traffic conditions. It is determined by measuring the depth (in tenths of a millimeter) that a standard needle penetrates the bitumen sample under specified conditions.

● **for 25 grades of bitumen**

$$\text{STANDARD PENETRATION} = (A+B+C) / 3$$

$$= 865/3$$

SPT = 33

SAMPLE	INITIAL	FINAL	TOTAL
A	133	164	295
B	123	150	297
C	133	162	273
		TOTAL	865

SAMPLE	INITIAL	FINAL	TOTAL
A	136	170	306
B	128	156	284
C	156	179	335
		TOTAL	925

Test on soil:

- For 35 grades of bitumen

$$\text{STANDARD PENETRATION} = (A+B+C) / 3$$

$$= 925/3$$

SPT = 33

SERIAL NO.	INITIAL TEMPERATURE (C)	FINAL TEMPERATURE (C)	GRADE OF BITUMEN
1.	31.5	60.2	A-25
2.	32	60.3	A-35

Ductility Test: Measures the ability of bitumen to stretch without breaking. It indicates flexibility and crack resistance, especially in cold climates. It is typically measured by the distance (in centimeter) a bitumen sample can be elongated under standard conditions before breaking.

Initial temperature = 25.5

Acceptable value = >50cm

$$\text{Total of mould 1\&2} = 78+66.5 = 144.5$$

$$= 144.5/2$$

$$= 72.25\text{cm}$$

SOIL COMPACTION (STANDARD PROCTOR TEST / HEAVY COMPACTION)

This test determines the optimal moisture content at which soil reaches its maximum dry density. Commonly done using the Standard Proctor Test or Modified Proctor Test.

1. Volume Of Mold = 1000 cm (Vm)
2. Weight of Empty Mold = 9.496 kg (Wm)
1. Fall of Rammer = 4.86 kg
2. Fall of Rammer = 450 mm
3. No. of Layer = 5
4. No. of blows per layer = 25
5. Specific gravity of soil (G) = 2.65

	8%	11%	15%	18%	21%
Wt. of mold + compacted soil	13.307	13.566	13.960	14.085	13.975
Wt. of compacted soil	3.811	4.070	4.464	4.589	4.479
Bulk density = W1-WM/VM	3.811	4.07	4.464	4.589	4.479
Dry density = Y/1+W	3.66	3.75	3.95	3.93	3.79

WATER CONTENT DETERMINATION-

The amount of water present in a soil sample. Usually performed using the oven drying method, where a soil sample is weighed, dried in an oven, and weighed again to calculate the water content.

CBR TEST (CALIFORNIA BEARING RATIO)

Assesses the strength of sub grade soil or base materials by measuring resistance to penetration. Higher CBR values indicate stronger soil suitable for road pavement design.

Penetration	Load drowing ring
0	0
0.5	0
1.0	0
1.50	0
2.00	0
2.5	14
3	0
4	0
5	22
7.50	0
10.00	0

	8%	11%	15%	18%	21%
Wt. of empty container (W1)	0.016	0.014	0.014	0.012	0.012
Wt. of container + soil (W2)	0.066	0.066	0.066	0.068	0.064
Wt. of container + Dry soil (W3)	0.064	0.062	0.060	0.060	0.056
Water content, $W = \frac{W2-W3}{W3-W1}$	0.041	0.083	0.13	0.167	0.181

$$2.5 = (14 \times 500) / 75 = (92.105 / 1370) \times 100 = 6.7\%$$

$$5 = (22 \times 500) / 75 = (144.73 / 2055) \times 100 = 7.05\%$$

C.B.R. value = 7.05%

RESULTS AND GRAPHS OF TEST PERFORMED

Bitumen Softening Point Test:

a. A-25 Grade: 60.2°C

b. A-35Grade:60.3°C

These results reflect good thermal stability, confirming that the bitumen is suitable for moderate to high-temperature conditions.

Fig. 1

Penetration Test:

a. Set 1 Average: 288.3

b. Set 2 Average:308.3 Moderate resistance is indicated, making it suitable for sub grade use in lighter traffic areas.

Ductility test:

Fig -2

Average Ductility = 72.25 cm,

Indicating excellent elasticity, making the bitumen ideal for surfaces exposed to thermal and load-induced stresses.

Fig- 3

Proctor Compaction Test:

- a. Maximum Dry Density (MDD) = ~3.95 g/cm³
- b. Optimum Moisture Content (OMC)=15%

These results enhance the load-bearing capacity and stability of the pavement.

Fig-4

Water Content Determination:

The water content ranged from 4.1% to 18.1%, supporting optimal moisture content for construction and ensuring durability.

Fig-5

CBR Test:

- a. CBR @ 2.5 mm: 6.7%
- b. CBR@5.0mm:7.05%
The soil is moderately strong, suitable for light traffic areas

Fig-6

Conclusion

The laboratory investigations conducted in this study confirm the technical suitability of pervious bituminous pavement for improving underpass drainage systems. The softening point, penetration, and ductility tests demonstrate that the selected grades of bitumen possess adequate thermal stability, flexibility, and hardness required for reliable pavement performance under moderate traffic and varying environmental conditions.

Similarly, the soil compaction and CBR test results indicate that the sub grade has sufficient strength and density to support pavement layers while ensuring durability and resistance to settlement. The water content values also align with optimal moisture requirements, contributing to the overall stability of the structure.

These findings validate the effectiveness of the chosen materials and design for sustainable storm water management. The use of laboratory data provides a strong foundation for informed decision-making in the implementation phase, ensuring that the proposed pervious pavement system can function effectively to reduce surface runoff, improve drainage, and enhance road safety in underpass areas.

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